

TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES, INSTRUCTIONAL INTERVENTIONS, AND THE LEVEL OF SCHOOL CHANGE READINESS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

MA. HERSLEY L. HERNANDEZ¹

ELISA N. CHUA, PHD²

mahersley.hernandez@deped.gov.ph¹

elisa.chua@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-7887-1469¹

0000-0003-1358-9953²

Bugtongnapulo Elementary School, Bugtongnapulo, Lipa City, Batangas, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of the school operations is influenced by several factors including the leadership potential of the school heads, the teacher's commitment to adapt to the changes, and the instructional interventions that are prevalent in an educational institution. The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship of these variables towards the attainment of the school change readiness in the North District, Division of Lipa City. The study employed descriptive quantitative correlational design administered to 163 respondents during the 3rd Quarter of the SY 2020-2021. The study uses a self-made survey questionnaire using google forms. The respondents highly perceived the effectiveness of instructional interventions and provided their perception that the change readiness is highly evidenced in the school. Findings of the study revealed that there is a positive correlation between the subcategories of the change readiness and all the four dimensions of transformational leadership practices. In addition, there is a positive correlation between the subcategories of the school change readiness and all the four dimensions of instructional interventions. Finally, teacher resource training and instructional facilitation and delivery were the two significant constructs that predict transformational leadership practices as well as instructional interventions that affect the change readiness of the teachers.

Keywords: Change Readiness, Transformational Leadership, Educational Instructional Intervention, Teacher's Training and Development